

STATE SERVICES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES SOME ASPECTS OF THE INDICATION

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Resolution ~~~ of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev of December 12, 2017 "On Measures for Fundamental Reform of the National System of Providing Public Services to the Population"

In the List of State Services Gradually Introduced in 2018-2020, Provided Only Through Public Service Centers on the "Single Window" Principle, approved by Decree No. UP-5278, 1) registration, deregistration, and registration at the place of stay; 2) the introduction of such public services as the issuance and extension of temporary residence permits (registration) is also aimed at solving problems in this area.

However, this is not all the public services provided by passport departments. It should be noted that today it is advisable to establish mechanisms for providing the following services related to the passport system through public service centers of justice bodies: 1) registration of a passport or identity document, granting the right to stay in the country; 2) registration of permanent registration or registration at the place of stay; 3) extension of the validity of entry visas for foreign citizens and stateless persons staying in the country, etc.

The Order of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 14, 2017, No. 147 "On Measures to Enhance the Conduct Culture of Internal Affairs Officers" sets the goal of effectively organizing the activities of internal affairs officers to improve the culture of conduct, as well as ensuring that employees in their activities fully and comprehensively comply with the principle of observing the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, as defined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies," and respecting these rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests, and improving the culture of conduct of employees and increasing their personal responsibility in this regard.

The proper organization of the civil service also depends on the legislative acts adopted in the state. The level of legal regulation of public service relations determines the trends in its development. Existing legislation in the state reflects the content and current state of the public service. In the civil service system, the level of elaboration of legislation and the correct establishment of the mechanism for its implementation are of great importance.

One of the important principles of the state service of internal affairs bodies is legality. Internal affairs bodies carry out their activities in accordance with the law and regulatory acts based on it.

According to the International Code of Conduct for Officials in the Public Service, adopted at the 82nd plenary session of the UN General Assembly on December 12, 1996, a state position is a position entrusted to the state and involving activities in the interests of the state. Therefore, civil servants must demonstrate absolute loyalty to the interests of the state, represented by the democratic institutions of power of their country. This, in turn, places

responsibility on civil servants for the competent and effective performance of their duties in accordance with the law.

It is known that civil servants are obliged to execute orders, directives, and other instructions of a higher state body (civil servant), except for those that contradict the law. Based on the principle of hierarchy of subordination of the civil service, civil servants are obliged to execute orders, directives, instructions, and other legal decisions of superiors issued within their competence on the basis of subordination.

Civil servants carry out all orders on the basis of personal responsibility. Therefore, the order received for execution must be assessed by the civil servant from the point of view of its compliance with legality and state interests. In order to fulfill their professional duties, civil servants are obliged to maintain and improve their qualification level.

When entering the civil service, a civil servant must be ready for the high-quality performance of official functions and professional duties. In its business characteristics, it must meet the requirements of the state position held.

An employee of the internal affairs body, as a civil servant, performs compulsory actions supplied by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other regulatory legal acts, constituting the essence of professional service activity. An employee of the internal affairs body acts on behalf of the state and on behalf of the state as a civil servant, therefore he must perform his duties in accordance with the provisions of the Constitution.

Over the past period, large-scale work has been carried out to improve the system of internal affairs bodies. Significant work has been carried out on the development and strengthening of the lower levels of internal affairs bodies, organized in mahallas to maintain public order, ensure the safety of citizens, prevent offenses, and combat crime.

The role of civil society institutions is also invaluable in further strengthening guarantees for the human being, their life, freedom, honor, dignity, and other inalienable rights, recognized as the highest value in Uzbekistan, and in realizing their aspirations.

The inextricable link between the concepts of independence, Constitution, civil society, and democracy is of paramount importance. Indeed, an independent country cannot be imagined without a democratic state governed by the rule of law and strong civil society institutions. Therefore, from the very first days of independence, the path of democratic renewal and building a free civil society was chosen in our country. Therefore, everyone takes this path in their own way. Based on the fundamental principles of democracy, strictly adhering to them, Uzbekistan at the same time carries out its actions in accordance with the thinking of our people, their millennial way of life.

Legality and law and order in society are established through the lawful actions of citizens, the observance of laws by all state bodies and public associations, and their proper use. Establishing stability, peace, and tranquility in society, ensuring unconditional observance of human rights and freedoms, is an important condition for achieving the goals set by the large-scale reforms being carried out in the country for further socio-economic development, improving the well-being of the population, and building a legal democratic state.

An integrated legal system has been created in the republic to protect the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, maintain public order, ensure the security of the individual, society, and the state, and prevent and suppress offenses, in which internal affairs bodies play an important role.

As noted above, internal affairs bodies perform the tasks of strengthening legality and law and order, protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens, and combating crime. They carry out inquiries and preliminary investigations in cases within their competence, and ensure peace and human security. The importance of the implementation of the functions of internal affairs bodies increases even more in the context of the formation of a state governed by the rule of law and the formation of civil society.

Over the past period, large-scale work has been carried out to improve the system of internal affairs bodies. Significant work has been carried out on the development and strengthening of the lower levels of internal affairs bodies, created in mahallas to maintain public order, ensure the safety of citizens, prevent offenses, and combat crime. Regarding the system of public services, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 4, 2018, "On Approving Certain Administrative Regulations for the Provision of Public Services in the Sphere of Internal Affairs Bodies" serves as an important legal basis for regulating the provision of public services by internal affairs bodies.

The Resolution specifies the administrative regulations for the provision of public services for the issuance of a certificate of criminal record, the procedure for the provision of public services for the provision of address information, in which the applicant applies to the Center for Public Services in person to receive the public service or registers on the Single Portal of Interactive Public Services of the Republic of Uzbekistan to receive public services electronically.

If the applicant or their close relatives (parents, spouse, and children) apply in person, an employee of the Center for Public Services fills out a questionnaire electronically on behalf of the applicant, and if they apply through the Single Portal of Interactive Public Services, independently, in accordance with the requirements established by the Regulation. When acting in the interests of third parties, a notarized power of attorney is attached to the request. In this case, a notarized power of attorney is not required when applying by lawyers in the interests of a third party on the basis of a contract (order). After filling out the questionnaire, the applicant verifies the accuracy of the information and confirms their electronic digital signature. In cases where it is impossible to confirm the application with an electronic digital signature in person, the corresponding signatures may also be confirmed by other means of identification (dactyloscopy, electronic signature, etc.) [2].

Implemented reforms During the visits of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the regions, memorandums of cooperation were signed on organizing training seminars on the topic "Procedure for using electronic public services" in cooperation with the Ministries of Preschool Education, Public Education, and Higher and Secondary Specialized Education in order to improve citizens' knowledge and skills in using public services, including online ones, and to ensure the accessibility of services provided through Public Service Centers to every family.

Also, in order to form a culture of applying to the Centers for Public Services for the use of relevant services, to explain the convenience and importance of applying to the Centers in electronic form, oral legal events are being organized, and visual promotional materials (brochures, flyers) are being distributed.

To summarize, in the sphere of legislative development, it is necessary to accelerate the adoption of the Law "On Public Service" and resolve issues aimed at increasing professional training and responsibility, personnel rotation, the effectiveness and efficiency of the control

mechanism, public accountability, systematization, preventing nepotism (in-law relations), parochialism, tribalism, cronyism, leadership, lobbying, and others that create the basis for conflicts of interest.

We also consider it expedient to strengthen liability in criminal legislation for such acts as abuse of office and illegal enrichment, as well as, based on the practice of foreign states, to adopt normative acts regulating the liability of legal entities and the confiscation of property acquired illegally, to improve the legal system for the protection of witnesses, experts, and victims of crime in national legislation, and to create a single independent agency for coordinating the anti-corruption system.

References:

1. See: National Database of Legislation, 05.10.2018, No 09/18/797/1998; 02.07.2019, No 09/19/548/3362, 29.12.2019, No 09/19/1046/4242, 30.12.2019, No 09/10/1049/4245; 15.01.2020, No 09/20/24/0053, 09.06.2020, No 09/20/364/0739, 29.09.2020, No 09/20/593/1340) 08.04.2021, No 09/21/189/0303, National Database of Legislation, 27.12.2021, No 09/21/774/1198.
2. See: National Database of Legislation, 02.07.2019, No. 09/19/548/3362.